

Grant Agreement No.: 101083805
Call: DIGITAL-2021-SKILLS-01
Topic: DIGITAL-2021-SKILLS-01-ANALYSIS
Type of action: DIGITAL-CSA

DIGITAL EUROPE PROGRAMME

ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS

Supporting the success of the DIGITAL Programme

24.10.2023 Projects Meeting Report

Revision: v1.1

31.05.2024

Authors:

Brendan Rowan (Editor) BluSpecs

Contributors:

Tanya Suarez	BluSpecs
Sam Jones	BluSpecs
Max Welford	BluSpecs
Nina Blessing	BluSpecs
Cristian Salis	BluSpecs
Juan José Navarro	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Eugenia Kyriotis	Martel Innovate
Spiros Borotis	Maggioli
Gabriel Rissola	HaDEA
Shirley Kavanagh	Trinity College Dublin
Simona Romeo	Alliance for IoT and Edge Innovation

Table of Contents

1	<i>Introduction</i>	5
1.1	Advanced Digital Skills within the DIGITAL Programme	5
1.2	Guiding policy ambitions – Digital Decade	5
1.3	Purpose of this report	6
1.4	Sources and contributions	7
2	<i>Methodology and approach</i>	9
2.1	Overview of approach towards collecting inputs	9
2.2	Defined Challenges	10
2.2.1	Selection of challenges	10
2.2.2	Challenges addressed	10
2.2.3	Categorisation and comparison	11
2.3	Collection of best practices and knowledge sharing	11
3	<i>Key results for addressing the key challenges in developing ADS</i>	12
3.1	Identification and analysis of underlying causes	12
3.1.1	Categorisation of key causes	12
3.1.2	Defining causes and impacts within challenges.....	12
3.2	Mapping the impact of challenges on identified stakeholders	18
3.3	Description of the causes and impact per challenge	20
3.3.1	Challenge 1: Rate of tech development and convergence.....	20
3.3.2	Challenge 2: Accessing the expertise for skilling.....	21
3.3.3	Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs.....	21
3.3.4	Challenge 4: Finding candidates at the right level	22
3.3.5	Challenge 5. The need for domain expertise and sectoral divergence in demands	23
3.3.6	Challenge 6: The leaky pipeline of women in digital	23
3.4	Identified actions for addressing challenges	25
3.4.1	Overview of proposed actions by type	25
4	<i>Key Learnings in Delivering advanced digital skills</i>	29
4.1	Identifying demand for course design	29
4.2	Building for sustainability and scale	30
5	<i>Conclusions</i>	32
5.1	Addressing the specifics of Advanced Digital Skills in the Digital Decade	32
5.2	Supporting European Industry	32
5.3	Priorities for actions	32
5.4	A call for coordinated mission from policy	33
5.5	Women in Digital – a systemic issue?	33
5.6	Ensuring the success and sustainability of programme investments	33
	<i>Annex 1 – Workshop Agenda</i>	35
	<i>Annex 2: Funded actions for reaching the Digital Decade Targets</i>	37
	Targetted PROGRAMMES, Networks, and clusters	39

Other Initiatives.....	39
Annex 3 – Project Brochure	40
Annex 4 – Challenge Scoping outcomes	49
Annex 5 - Identified actions.....	54

Abbreviations:

ADS	Advanced Digital Skills
ADT	Advanced Digital Technologies
BoD	Board of Directors
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DG-CNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DIGITAL	Digital Europe Programme
DSJP	Digital Skills and Jobs Platform
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HEI	Higher Education Institution
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SPECIALISED	Funded actions for developing specialised Master's courses under DIGITAL
VET	Vocational Education and Training

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Advanced Digital Skills within the DIGITAL Programme

Over the past decade, significant progress has been made in the areas of advanced technologies. While the advances take hold, like other world regions Europe (EU) is still struggling to tackle the emerging gaps in advanced digital skills, ensuring access to high-quality digital training and skills for workers and citizens.

Over the next 5 years, Europe will need between 3.5 million and 13.9 million of new advanced digital skills professionals.¹ There will be a significant increase in demand for all advanced digital skills with a fourfold times increase in data analysis, AI application development and AI implementation, compared to demand in 2020.² A particular challenge is that the role of advanced digital talent is central to the competitiveness of European industry, to adapt and recover global leadership while at the same time ensuring that the tech of the future is aligned with the Declaration on Digital Rights and Principals.

As technology continues to rapidly advance, its potential benefits will extend across society. To ensure this transformation works effectively for Europeans and fosters ongoing inclusive and shared prosperity, a consistent supply of talent will be crucial.

The Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL Programme) is the European Union's flagship funding programme promoting and supporting the digital transformation of European society and economy³. It primarily focuses on fostering digital innovation and the development of advanced digital technologies. The programme provides funding for various projects in crucial areas such as supercomputing, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and advanced digital skills. Its main goals include enhancing Europe's competitiveness in the global digital landscape, ensuring digital inclusion and accessibility, and strengthening the EU's digital sovereignty. Through financial support and collaborative efforts, the programme aims to drive digital advancements and digitalisation across Europe.

The actions under Strategic Objective 4, Advanced Digital Skills, in the Work Programme 2021-2024 are aiming to support the excellence of EU education and training institutions in digital areas, including by encouraging their cooperation with research and business. The goal is to improve the capacity to nurture and attract digital talent, whilst fostering an ecosystem that will help drive innovation and digital breakthroughs. These actions aim to contribute to deliver on the *Digital Decade* targets.

1.2 Guiding policy ambitions – Digital Decade

The Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 establishes a framework for monitoring and collaborative mechanisms designed to realise shared goals and objectives for Europe's digital transformation. The skills pillar of the Digital Decade policy programme includes the target of having 20 million ICT specialists by 2030 while also emphasising the pursuit of gender convergence.

¹ LEADS Market Study (2023), LEADS Consortium

² LEADS D1.3 Final ADS Demand and Forecast Report 2023 (2023), LEADS Consortium

³ [European Commission, Digital Europe Programme](#)

Figure 1. Targets and objectives of Europe's Digital Decade

Currently only 47% of the target of 20 million employed ICT specialists has been achieved.⁴ This requires a substantial acceleration and deepening of both EU and Member State action. Fundamentally, the realisation of significant benefits from EU investments hinges on the availability of skilled people, able to develop, implement and use digital technologies and applications.

1.3 Purpose of this report

Under the Specific Objective 4 of the Digital Europe Programme, multiple skills actions were funded. This report provides a summary, analysis, and key takeaways of the inputs received through an in-person consultation and workshop held with stakeholders from within those actions. In order to provide constructive inputs towards the achievement of the Digital Decade targets.

In providing constructive and specific inputs towards reaching the targets, this document outlines identified challenges in the delivery of advanced digital skills programmes, and subsequently, practitioner-led ideas for actions that could address these identified key challenges.

The principal target audience is policy makers, with the goal of providing a deeper understanding of the specificities and particular contexts that affect the development of productive talent pools with the required advanced digital skills. It also serves as a reference for education and training providers with opportunities for the design, delivery and sustainability of courses and programmes.

The report is structured in the following sections:

- Section 3 provides an overview of the approach and methodology for consultations and scope of engagements

⁴ Report on the state of the Digital Decade (2023), European Commission

- Section 4 provides the outcomes of exploring causes related to key challenges identified and subsequent actions that can overcome such challenges.
- Section 5 includes the key learnings from practitioner-led round-table discussions on the design, delivery and sustainability of advanced digital skills master’s and training programmes.
- Section 6 provides a summary of conclusions for supporting the ADS component of the Digital Europe Programme.
- Annexes are provided that include the agenda, stakeholders, from each challenge and direct outputs.

1.4 Sources and contributions

The content of this report is the result of a consultation workshop with invited coordinators and representatives of the funded initiatives under the Advanced Digital Skills Strategic Objective of the DIGITAL programme.

This event took place on the 24th October 2023 in Brussels and was hosted with the European Commission DG CNECT, Unit G2 Interactive Technologies, Digital for Culture and Education, in coordination with the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), and supported by the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) Leading Europe’s Advanced Digital Skills (LEADS).

A total of 68 individuals participated in the workshop from the following clusters⁵:

- CEF Masters in AI (6)
- Short-term Training Courses (15)
- SPECIALISED Masters – 2021 (11)
- SPECIALISED Masters – 2022 (5)
- Support Initiatives – LEADS, DSJP, DS4Skills, EmpowerED (14)
- EC/HaDEA (17)

Each of these participants represented various stakeholders, with the largest population coming from HEI followed by industry associations and representative organisations.

The workshop was delivered in two formats providing the inputs contained here within.

⁵ See Annex 2 for details on each Cluster

The first format consisted of 2 round-table discussions with project representatives providing their own experience, learnings and best practice.

The second format was a facilitated workshop delivered in teams that addressed predefined challenges identified by the LEADS consortium through the engagement of the ADS Topic Groups in the 6 months prior.

The agenda for this event is provided as a reference in Annex 1 of this report.

2 METHODOLOGY AND APPROACH

2.1 Overview of approach towards collecting inputs

The structure for developing recommendations and identification of best practice was challenge-based. The contributions were provided in the context of 6 identified challenges that were explored in detail to provide an assessment of their underlying causes, the impact of the challenge on specific stakeholders and then the identification and ideation of actions that would provide solutions to the challenges.

Key definitions applied:

- **Causes** - The causes behind each of the challenges, i.e. the constituent factors which have led to said challenge becoming an issue.
- **Impacts** - The diverse impacts that each of the respective challenges exert on various stakeholders
- **Actions** - Potential actions that can be taken, both intervention actions and policy actions, which can aid in remedying the impacts felt by the stakeholder groups.

Figure 2. Overview of the challenge-based approach for stakeholder contributions.

The process included the following steps:

- Challenge Exploration
 - Validation of challenge definition and description.
 - Identification of key causes which contribute to the challenge and classification within the PESTLE framework.
 - Description of the impact of the challenge on key stakeholder categories: Education, Training, Industry, Learners.
- Solution Scoping
 - Ideation of potential actions.
 - Selection and prioritisation of top actions.

- Relative assessment of the cost-benefit of each action.

As a means of comparing causes and actions across all challenges, the received inputs were grouped and categorised for analysis of the priority causes to be addressed and the types of actions recommended.

2.2 Defined Challenges

2.2.1 Selection of challenges

The challenges selected were proposed based on the analysis conducted by the LEADS consortium both from within the published gap analysis and the engagement with the ADS actions through the established cross-portfolio Topic Groups.⁶ The proposed selection was based on the ubiquity of the challenges and the relevance to the Digital Decade targets.

These were then validated with responsible officers from the EC and HaDEA which provided the final selection. The selected challenges were provided to the participants, who provided a reviewed description and definition of each challenge.

2.2.2 Challenges addressed

- **Challenge 1: Rate of tech development and convergence – skills fit for industry**

Companies and other organisations struggle to adopt quickly enough to rapid technological developments and technology convergence. This creates a mismatch between available and needed skills which makes it difficult to leverage new value chain opportunities and presents a difficulty for the education and training community to keep up.

- **Challenge 2: Accessing the expertise for skilling – the bottleneck in developing the advanced digital talent pool**

The capacity for educational and training providers to source their own talent for delivering programmes and initiatives is limiting the overall delivery of advanced digital skills. The Access to experts and individuals with the right knowledge and own skills, with the flexibility required for the development of advanced digital skills initiatives is hindering the development of more digital specialists and experts.

- **Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs**

Challenge 3 represents “Addressing SMEs”, posing the question over how we should take the large variety of SMEs’ adoption of technologies into account, as well as their limited resources, shorter planning horizons, and limited visibility, in the context of their roles as training and skilling partners and as beneficiaries. It further addressed how we can address the need to support non-ICT specialists and multi-role individuals present in SMES.

- **Challenge 4: Finding candidates at the right level – the supply of candidates for very advanced programmes**

For many advanced skills profiles there is a double challenge, firstly there is often a high barrier to entry in terms of existing skills and knowledge requirements for candidates to participate, e.g. prior STEM graduates. In addition, for the highly specialised profiles there is a limited

⁶ D4.1 Topic Group Report (2023), LEADS Consortium

critical mass for the participants which impacts on feasibility and investment potential in some courses.

- **Challenge 5: The need for domain expertise and sectoral divergence in demands**

In the development of advanced digital talent, technical skills are not sufficient. Especially as we advance in new technologies, domain expertise is becoming more important and necessary. Both contextual and sectoral knowledge is required for the development of solutions and applications that meet the needs of the industry and achieve productivity. It has been observed that, in order to become productive, it can take up to two years for a technical profile to develop sufficient expertise in the application domains.

- **Challenge 6: The leaky pipeline of women in digital**

Through each stage of the STEM education cycle, through primary, secondary and tertiary and following on into the workplace, there is a drop off in the participation of women compared to men at each transition. The end result is that women are occupying fewer roles in engineering, research and production compared to their male counterparts. The gender imbalance observed in digital specialists is the result of many structural and social factors along the talent supply chain.

2.2.3 Categorisation and comparison

Once the causes were collected for each respective challenge, these were then categorised into 11 wider categories, based on the nature of the cause. This allowed for further analysis and trend identification. These categories are outlined in section 4.2.1, with a detailed description of each category, including examples.

2.3 Collection of best practices and knowledge sharing

The inputs for section 5 of the report were derived from 2 moderated round-table discussion:

- Meeting the Needs of the Digital Decade: Open discussion on the key areas of Advanced digital skills that are required for the Digital Europe Programme
 - Tanya Suárez (M) (LEADS), Asja Satler (DG CNECT), Barry Feeney (Human Centered AI Masters), Ilker Demirkol (MERIT), Minna Isomursu (REBOOT SKILLS)
- Generating greater sustainability of actions – strategies and opportunities
 - Óscar Rodríguez Díaz (M) (HaDEA), Claudio Feijóo (AI4Gov), Christos Karras (TRUST-FOOD), Maria do Carmo Gomes (ManagiDiTH), Christos Douligeris (CyberSecPro)

3 KEY RESULTS FOR ADDRESSING THE KEY CHALLENGES IN DEVELOPING ADS

3.1 Identification and analysis of underlying causes

3.1.1 Categorisation of key causes

Across all addressed challenges, the causes identified were collected and clustered within a set of categories in order to facilitate the analysis and identification of those causes most prevalent across all challenges and to compare the differences between the challenges.

The categories identified from workshop responses are provided in alphabetical order:

Administrative burden	The excessive paperwork and procedures, for example, involved in developing and delivering advanced digital skills training programmes.
Awareness	The lack of understanding among individuals, businesses, and policymakers about the importance and benefits of advanced digital skills.
Barriers to access	The obstacles that prevent individuals from participating in advanced digital skills training, such as geographic location, financial constraints, or lack of time.
Cost of delivery	The high cost of developing and delivering high-quality advanced digital skills training programmes.
Fragmentation	The lack of coordination and standardisation among different providers of advanced digital skills training, leading to duplication of effort and confusion for learners.
Limited resources	The scarcity of financial, human, and technological resources to support the development and delivery of advanced digital skills training.
Return of Investment (ROI)	The difficulty in measuring the return of investment for advanced digital skills training programmes, making it challenging to identify and act on priorities.
Speed of evolution	The rapid pace of change in the digital landscape, which requires ongoing training and upskilling to keep up.
Status Quo	The resistance to change and the preference for traditional methods of training, which can hinder the adoption of advanced digital skills training.
Systemic	The deep-rooted challenges within education and training systems that make it difficult to adapt to the demands of the digital economy.
Talent source	The difficulty in attracting and retaining top talent in the field of advanced digital skills training.
Administrative burden	The excessive paperwork and procedures, for example, involved in developing and delivering advanced digital skills training programmes.
Awareness	The lack of understanding among individuals, businesses, and policymakers about the importance and benefits of advanced digital skills.

3.1.2 Defining causes and impacts within challenges

3.1.2.1 Common causes across challenges

In the figure below, the number of categories challenges are compared by the number of challenges where they were present, and the absolute number reported by workshop participants. For causes relating to both Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs and Challenge 5: The

need for domain expertise, where a category has appeared in both challenges, the number was reduced by half to provide a fair comparison in terms of scale and importance.

As can be observed, the top 5 causes impeding advanced digital skills development identified are: **Barriers to Access, Status Quo, Fragmentation, Speed of Evolution and Return on Investment (ROI).**

Figure 3. Mapping of the key categories of causes by distribution across challenges and volume of causes. Data points have been jittered and number of recorded causes for Challenges 3 and 5 have been halved to provide fair comparison.

Among other categories it was noticed that Systematic causes, are particularly niche – despite having a high number of causes, it was localised on just two challenges, the majority of which fall under Challenge 6: Leaky Pipeline of Women in Digital.

Below, each of the categories of causes are discussed in detail provided in order of relevance.

Barriers to Access

Reported causes in this category appeared a total of 9 times and **are present across all six challenges**. Barriers to access can manifest in various forms, affecting both education and innovation. Key issues here exist in areas such as the effects of socioeconomic inequality on access to ADS training, including the recognition of prior learning. Individuals, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds, may find the cost of accessing training programmes prohibitive, exacerbating existing barriers. Within each challenge the barriers are different, the following items are evidence of this variability:

- Lack of access to technology & use of private sector tech labs in education.
- SMEs lack specific funding instruments to benefit from universities
- Financial capacity to participate in courses.

Financial barriers also pose significant obstacles, preventing individuals and companies from fully participating in the digital skills development opportunities. This can further limit an individual's ability to attend courses or pursue advanced training. While similarly SMEs may struggle to secure the necessary funding for specialised training. This suggests that economic constraints may prevent some organisations or companies from enabling technology education, in turn impacting their long-term ability to deploy and utilise cutting-edge technology. It was, however, noted that geography plays a role too, with the distance to centres of knowledge and training having an inversely proportional impact on access, in spite of online and remote offerings.

Fragmentation

All challenges are impacted by fragmented coordination across diverse stakeholders is apparent, requiring systematic and coordinated actions. The absence of EU-wide frameworks and coordinated policy supports impedes the establishment of standardised approaches and combined efforts for advanced technology education and adoption. This results in a disjointed and fragmented arrangement of stakeholders. Addressing these critical issues becomes imperative for fostering a cohesive and effective landscape in advanced technology and education adoption.

This encapsulates:

- Institutions not having the necessary engagement with industry to discuss academic issues, including the creation and modification of courses.
- Lack of communication between training stakeholders and (industry) sectors

From a practical and operational perspective, the problem of fragmentation is complex and layered. Key issues encompass the need to equip organisations with essential skills that cultivate cross-disciplinary mindsets, bridge communication gaps and ensure common visions and missions.

Speed of Evolution in Digital Technologies

The rate of evolution in digital technologies was found to be a cause in 4 challenges, with a particular impact on the deployment tech solutions, policy and skills frameworks. Examples of identified causes include:

- Rapid job displacement and transformation.
- Lack of an up-to-date common framework and recognition; lack of standardised certifications and accreditation which are current and applicable.
- Speed of tech development is fast, with the education sector struggling to keep up with integrating and addressing developments in their courses.

Across all causes, it was found that the **lack of up-to-date standardised certifications and accreditations** is the most critical since they address the growing need for responsible innovation and the validation of skills in a rapidly changing technological landscape. Furthermore, standardised certifications and accreditations are essential for ensuring the recognition and validation of competencies across European companies and regions.

Return on Investment (ROI)

The lack of a visible or unclear ROI was of particular relevance for the Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs where almost of two-thirds of causes were related to this category. This category is a major limiting factor on the investment from companies both in terms of time and financial resources. Even in cases where training is heavily subsidised or free, it is not clear if the productive time lost by the employee will produce future competitiveness gains. Related to this is the case, where an organisation knows it needs to upskill or invest in digitalisation but cannot identify which investments to make in terms of people or skills. The lack of clarity on the market demand for ADS, making it difficult for stakeholders to justify the investment in ADS adoption. This perceived gap may result in a reluctance to embrace new technologies, despite the significant potential benefits that can be derived.

Specific causes reported included:

- The lack of an incentivisation system at policy level to ensure that companies understand the importance of training and act upon this.
- Lack of market demand for products / services needing advanced technology.

A critical point worth addressing is the role of leadership in shaping the technological trajectory of SMEs. Leaders who fail to recognise the importance of ADS and adopt short-term visions can hinder the adoption of advanced technologies within their organisations. The inability to articulate long-term benefits of ADS and effectively communicate its potential impact can lead to missed opportunities for innovation and growth, and later negatively impact markets through diminished demand and deployment of services. There is, however, a realistic expectation that can be placed on small and medium companies and teams when demand is not immediate, immediate risks to turnover and profitability will take precedence (see Limited Resources below).

Status Quo

Across four challenges, the concept of the Status Quo was reported. This was particularly notable for Challenge 2: Accessing the expertise for skilling. It was believed that the process of creating or even modifying university degrees lacks in agility in respect to its: “Internal design, Curriculum design, Institutional approval, Accreditation process and Student enrolment”.

Further examples of causes under the Status Quo category include:

- The practical adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) is hindered by a confluence of societal and educational barriers.
- Rigidity of education system (teaching methods, length, difficulty in altering programmes, lack of “thinking outside the box”).

Within education, the outdated programme structures, and a general resistance to innovation is believed to make it difficult to prepare students for the demands of the digital economy. This inertia of the maintenance of status quo further impedes the adoption of AI and other advanced technologies in skilling and talent management and restricts the effectiveness of any investments made.

Administrative Burdens

Navigating funding processes introduces complexities and bureaucratic hurdles that hinder the advancement of digital skills. The intricate reporting requirements and cash flow constraints related to securing funding make it both financially and administratively burdensome for entities focusing on advancing digital skills. Additionally, rigid procurement policies and a lack of comprehensive economic strategies contribute to the overall administrative challenges, impeding the choice and speed of reaction for companies and organisations.

Awareness

A lack of understanding regarding the importance and benefits of ADS among individuals, businesses, and policymakers presents a significant barrier to their advancement in Europe. Individuals may not recognise the crucial role these skills play in career development and job market competitiveness, leading to a reluctance to invest in acquiring them. This reluctance perpetuates a skills gap, leaving individuals ill-prepared for the demands of a digitalised economy and hindering their access to high-quality job opportunities. Similarly, businesses, particularly SMEs, that underestimate the value of advanced digital skills may be hesitant to invest in training their workforce or adopting new technologies, thereby impeding innovation and competitiveness.

Cost of Delivery

The substantial investment required for developing and implementing high-quality advanced digital skills training programmes is a significant barrier to their widespread adoption. This investment covers various aspects, including the development of an up-to-date curriculum, acquisition of cutting-edge technology infrastructure, and recruitment of skilled instructors. For many organisations, especially smaller businesses and educational institutions, the financial burden of such programmes can discourage participation, often leading to compromises in programme quality or accessibility. Moreover, the ongoing evolution of digital technologies necessitates continuous updates to training programmes to remain relevant. This further escalates the financial strain on organisations already struggling with limited resources.

Limited Resources

This category is closely related to ROI, as two sides of the coin – when the investment case is clear, the access to resourcing still acts as a barrier. Businesses often grapple with constraints on both human and financial resources, presenting a dual challenge when it comes to addressing the future demand for advanced digital talent.

Digital transformation necessitates a skilled workforce capable of navigating complex digital landscapes. However, building and nurturing such talent requires substantial investments in training, recruitment, and retention initiatives, which may strain already stretched resources. Furthermore, the competition for skilled digital talent is fierce, with demand often outpacing supply in key areas such as data analysis, cybersecurity, and artificial intelligence.

In this context, businesses face the challenge of balancing short-term operational priorities with the imperative of building a future-ready workforce. The immediate pressures of day-to-

day operations and limited resources can make it difficult for businesses to allocate sufficient attention and resources to ADS talent development initiatives.

Systemic

In total, 9 causes were categorised as systemic with eight out of nine belonging to the Challenge 6: Leaky Pipeline of Women in Digital. This concentration underscores a dominance of systemic issues within this specific challenge. The other cause relates to the challenge of finding candidates at the correct skill level for the existing vacancy or course.

Specific causes here include:

- Lack of appropriate guidance or role models
- Technology industry, especially in software development roles, predominantly lacks diverse perspectives and input from women.

This concentration of systemic causes within the lack of women in tech challenge sheds light on the pervasive influence of systemic factors in certain domains. It prompts reflection on the complexity of tackling distinct challenges, suggesting that addressing systemic issues within a specific context may require nuanced and targeted strategies, given their overarching impact on the challenge in question.

Talent Source

Causes associated with a limited supply of talent with the necessary prior knowledge or experience to participate in ADS programmes were observed across two challenges. One cause relates to a demographic shift, characterised by a growing proportion of young workers entering the workforce, which presents a novel and unique set of challenges. While this demographic shift could potentially replenish the talent pool, it also raises concerns about the effective integration of these young workers into the rapidly evolving digital landscape. Compounding this challenge is the pre-existing shortage of skilled workers in the ICT sector. This has created a significant bottleneck in developing the advanced digital talent pool required to support the ever-expanding digital economy.

3.1.2.2 Summary of distribution of causes across challenges

In the figure below, the distribution of the cause categories and relative volume is shown. Administrative Burden, Cost of Delivery, Limited Resources, Systemic, and Talent Source are the categories more closely related to specific challenges while Barriers to Access, Fragmentation and Stasis Quo are the most widespread.

Figure 4. Distribution of the causes by category across challenges.

From a challenge perspective, the Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs is found to have the widest range of causes, followed by the Rate of Technology Development and Convergence, Need for Domain Expertise, and Accessing the Expertise for Skilling. The Leaky Pipeline of Women in Digital was the most concentrated.

3.2 Mapping the impact of challenges on identified stakeholders

During the exploration of the challenges, the participants were asked to assess the impact of each challenge on four loosely defined stakeholder groups: Education, Industry, Learners/Trainees and Training/VET.

As shown in Figure 5, below, the nature of each challenge affected different stakeholder groups differently. There is a variation in the number of impacts identified by each team that is the result of a combination of time available and clarity of the challenge to begin with. Perhaps reflecting the profiles of participants, it was seen that the greatest impacts identified appear to affect Education stakeholders while the fewest are related to Training and VET stakeholders.

Figure 5: Chartered analysis of defined impacts of each challenge on each of the four stakeholder groups.

The education sector faces multifaceted challenges in preparing a workforce equipped for the demands of the advanced technology sector. This group appears to feel the impact the most, accounting for a total of 16 causes across all challenge categories.

These impacts identified are based on the inability to keep pace with rapid technological advancements, provide requisite skills and knowledge and adapt to disruptive changes. A skills mismatch persists between available technology and the skills imparted through education. These impacts emphasise the need for more interdisciplinary and domain-specific education. Attracting and retaining top talent in the advanced technology sector requires educational initiatives that align with its dynamic landscape.

Industry is impacted by the requirement for a long-term vision, continuous innovation, and effective collaboration. Short-term visions among industry players limit the impact of Advanced Digital Technologies (ADT), leading to missed opportunities for innovation and growth. Key impacts discussed included a lack of competitiveness resulting from failure to incorporate diverse perspectives in product design, the limitation in developing students into industry experts through weak collaboration between SMEs and HEIs. In general, it is believed that the lack of effective collaboration mechanisms hinders innovation, talent development, and the adoption of advanced technologies within the SME sector.

Critical weaknesses lie in aligning corporate strategies with long-term innovation and growth, ensuring a tech-savvy workforce, effectively utilising advanced technologies, and fostering knowledge exchange and partnerships between SMEs and HEIs. Additionally, the lack of a large pool of talent can make it difficult for companies to find the workers they need, especially in high-demand fields.

When it comes to how Learners and Trainees are impacted by the select challenges, they were the second most represented of all four stakeholders. Hereby it appears that the skills gap that are being taught and those that employers demand is significantly impacted by the rapid

pace of technological change, a lack of alignment between education and industry and the general lack of inclusivity in education and training.

This ultimately amounts to limited career progression, low employability, dissatisfaction and low motivation, and vulnerability to societal challenges. Prioritising these critical points is essential for navigating the challenges and shaping an education landscape that effectively reach and are accurately tailored to the ability of Learners / Trainees.

Training stakeholders struggle in keeping up with the changing demands of the workforce, leading to the current system of training and vocational education (VET) is not producing enough skilled workers to meet the needs of the economy, this is resulting from an identified lack of work-based learning programmes. Work-based learning programmes can provide students with the hands-on experience they need to succeed in the workforce, while trainers can help students develop the skills they need to be competitive.

3.3 Description of the causes and impact per challenge

3.3.1 Challenge 1: Rate of tech development and convergence

The challenge at hand often stems from companies adopting a short-term vision, resulting in insufficient investment in reskilling initiatives. This lack of commitment hinders their ability to keep pace with the rapid advancements in technology. Reskilling and internal skilling actions are crucial, given the limited number of specialists in these areas. However, there is hesitance towards embracing new technological specialists, primarily due to direct cost concerns.

This challenge is notably pronounced in SMEs, where the potential for high costs may not immediately translate into increased profits, especially if there is limited market demand for products or services requiring advanced technology. This financial strain can impede their ability to invest in the necessary expertise to stay technologically competitive.

Moreover, certain policies such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) underscore the need for better governance over new technologies. This governance is essential not only for compliance but also to effectively address social issues like data management. Ensuring prompt and effective responses to the rapid development of technology is crucial, and improved policies play a pivotal role in achieving this objective.

Interestingly, it is noted that a lack of structured interest, opinions and potential detractors of advanced technology contributes to the challenge. There is a prevailing inclination to maintain the status quo, hindering the necessary shift towards adopting new technologies and impeding digital transformation. The reluctance to change is a formidable barrier, preventing companies from leveraging the benefits of advanced technology.

Furthermore, the post-Covid era has brought about an acceleration in digital transformation, yet it faces a significant hurdle: the non-ICT workers and their ability to uptake new technologies. The challenge lies in bridging the gap between existing skill sets and the demands of rapidly evolving technologies.

Impacts

While education is affected, it was industry in particular where the impact of this challenge was felt strongest, as the challenge of the rapid pace of tech development and misalignment induces a short-term focus in companies, hampering long term vision.

3.3.2 Challenge 2: Accessing the expertise for skilling

The insufficient promotion and recognition of digital skills throughout the educational journey contribute significantly to this challenge. Barriers to access were found to compound the issue; lack of availability of private sector tech labs in education and a scarcity of individuals possessing specialised knowledge intensify competition. This scarcity not only affects access but also increases costs, as sourcing expertise from abroad can prove to be an expensive solution. Additionally, in the European Union, the public sector must compete with private industry salaries to secure and retain skilled professionals, particularly impacting the appeal of teaching careers in higher education where salary is just one aspect of attractiveness.

Fragmentation compounds the challenges in integrating ADS into existing courses across diverse disciplines such as agriculture or health. This lack of awareness is perpetuated by institutions limited engagement with the industry, resulting in a lack of critical feedback on academic matters, especially in course creation and modification.

This context is closely tied to the prevailing status quo within institutions, which exhibits inflexibility in various aspects, ranging from internal design, curriculum design, institutional approval, accreditation, and finally student enrolment. This lack of agility hinders adaptation and responsiveness to the evolving needs of digital education.

In linkage with the structural limitations mentioned in the former section, including restructured access to private sector labs, hinders hands-on learning experiences crucial for practical skill development. This limitation not only worsens challenges in finding qualified candidates for specialised roles, but also hampers access to the expertise necessary for skilling initiatives. This underscores the cascading nature of the issue, manifesting into diverse challenges throughout the education ecosystem.

The impact of this challenge suggests that there are difficulties in accessing the right expertise for skill development, with education and learners/trainees affected heavily. This suggests a need for better resources, qualified instructors, or relevant industry professionals in the educational or training programmes. Specifically for **Education**, the bottleneck in advancing the digital talent pool poses challenges for education. Limited funding, primarily reliant on public sources, constrains the establishment of comprehensive programmes. Additionally, the slow attraction of students from diverse backgrounds to ICT at the primary stage delays the cultivation of essential digital skills.

3.3.3 Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs

In navigating the complexities of today's landscape, SMEs encounter a series of intertwined challenges that span policy, economic, technological, and legal domains.

While funding for SMEs to adopt new technologies is prevalent, it is often believed to be too complex in terms of the administrative effort that would have to be invested. This, combined with a lack of perspective on how an investment in ADS can yield greater revenue and the prioritisation of other investment areas than ADS, that seem more urgent, can be seen as root cause for the lack of SMEs engagement within the field of ADS.

A notable deficit hinders the incorporation of new technologies, particularly for non-ICT specialists and those playing diverse roles. The absence of effective integration policies leaves a void that is further widened by the lack of cohesion within the EU. This economic challenge is compounded by the absence of a visible reward system for companies that prioritise

training. This not only impedes them from internalising the importance of staff development, but also underscores a broader issue – the limited support for women in upskilling endeavours. This shortfall in support, particularly in sectors like the tech industry, entrepreneurship, and post-maternity leave scenarios, adds a significant layer to the economic challenge SMEs face.

Pertaining to the technological landscape, SMEs grapple with a shortage of staff possessing basic digital skills necessary to harness novel technologies. This scarcity, often confined to IT departments, highlights a critical capability gap.

In the legal realm, legislative developments such as the AI Act, GDPR, and Digital Services & Markets Act play a vital role, significantly impacting SMEs. The repercussions extend beyond compliance, compelling businesses to reshape their models to align with evolving legal landscape. Even with the employment of ICT specialists, a lack of comprehensive knowledge about legal requirements adds complexity to compliance efforts.

The challenge related to SMEs appears to be more critical for industry and learners/trainees. This is in line with the fact that SMEs play a significant role in the practical application of skills and will need tailored educational and training programmes going forward.

In the case of **Education**, the challenge of addressing SMEs has notable impacts. Firstly, institutions struggle to match the swift pace of disruptive technological changes, impeded by a lack of recourses for effective and rapid implementation. This lack in responsiveness hinders the agility needed to equip students with up-to-date skills. Additionally, the absence of adequate attention to the application of ADS in business courses compounds the challenge.

For **Learners and Trainees**, the impact is felt in various ways. There is a mismatch between the skills needed and available training, leading to a disparity between demand and supply. Limited course options from universities result in diminished interest and motivation among participants. Furthermore, academia struggles to keep pace with technological evolution, contributing to a lack of career progression and limited employability for learners.

For **Industry**, the challenge of addressing SMEs is multifaceted. Limited worker mobility in the EU constrains talent acquisition and growth. SMEs' vulnerability to cyber-attacks poses a significant threat, impacting competitiveness. Additionally, a lack of agility may cause them to miss opportunities for innovation and growth.

3.3.4 Challenge 4: Finding candidates at the right level

Given the current market demand for advanced digital skills, there is a clear incentive for individuals in related fields to upskill in advanced specialisations. However, this requires a significant amount of personal initiative, as there is a lack of role models showcasing the benefits, both on an industry-wide scale and a personal level, of pursuing such specialisations. Compounding this issue is the absence of accessible test funds and open laboratories for individuals to experiment with new technologies, hindering the crucial first contact with advanced tech, and posing a barrier to entry.

Companies, driven by immediate needs, often neglect long-term investment in their workforce's skills. Advanced degrees are not commonly offered at earlier stages of education, limited alternative education paths for individuals. Moreover, the absence of advanced digital tools in certain sectors creates a paradox – while candidates may acquire advanced knowledge, the market's inability to utilise this newfound expertise discourages their

application. This underscores the necessity for companies to align their adoption of advanced tech with the availability of skilled candidates.

The adoption of advanced technology also demands a sense of personal responsibility. Without clear role models to guide individuals on this path, there is a diminished supply of candidates willing to participate in advanced programmes, exacerbating the skills gap.

This challenge is pronounced in the education sector, which indicates potential difficulties in identifying candidates with appropriate skill levels. This suggests a need for improved screening processes or alignment between education and industry requirements. The challenge of finding candidates for highly advanced programmes impacts the sector in various ways. Academia faces reputational damage, due to the scarcity of suitable candidates, resulting in a limited pool of individuals willing to pursue and acquire the necessary skills. Consequently, there is a shortage of professionals trained in ADT and ADS.

3.3.5 Challenge 5. The need for domain expertise and sectoral divergence in demands

Amidst the challenges faced in educational programmes for tech advancements, a central issue arises from the specificity of courses. This specificity not only limits potential stakeholders but also escalates costs for relevant parties. Yet, the repercussions extend beyond financial constraints, delving into a deeper challenge – the divide between strategic and technical roles. This divide leads to a mutual lack of understanding between these critical facets of the educational landscape.

Zooming out to a broader perspective, the challenge is amplified by insufficient communication among stakeholders. This communication gap results in the emergence of gaps, mismatches, and a shortage of synergies, impeding the identification of sectoral and contextual knowledge necessary for educational programmes. This challenge is exacerbated by fragmented funding structures, hindering cross-sectoral engagement, thus perpetuating existing gaps.

A critical cause of this challenge is the absence of multidisciplinary approaches in formal education, leading to the development of overly sectoral programmes. This lack of flexibility within education systems presents a dual challenge: struggling to keep pace with rapid tech advancements and incorporating practical, sector-specific content.

The challenge of meeting domain expertise and sectoral demands is perceived more strongly in the education sector, emphasising the importance of aligning educational programmes with industry requirements. The lower score in training VET may suggest a relatively better adaptation in vocational training.

Within **Industry**, this challenge hinders progress in several ways. Primarily, there is a lack of collaboration between SMEs and HEIs, limiting access to specialised knowledge. This is accentuated by the impediment of the seamless transfer of students into industry-ready experts.

3.3.6 Challenge 6: The leaky pipeline of women in digital

This challenge stands out due to its systemic nature, encompassing various interconnected issues that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in advanced digital skills.

The pervasive dominance of white males within the industry remains a significant barrier. Particularly in fields like software development, there's a perception of male dominance, necessitating greater efforts to encourage the participation of women. In gaming, often seen as an entry point to the digital world for young males, women make up a small share of developers, leading to less input from women in the development process, which can make games less appealing to young women, who are then less likely to pursue a career in the industry. This creates a vicious cycle which marginalises the impact that women can have in the industry.

Ingrained gender imbalances and bias remain stubbornly present in both the education journey and within the workplace, especially when it comes to IT and STEM. Today, even how the emerging advanced technologies developed, can serve to reinforce, and grow these biases. The lack of women role models and mentorship further exacerbates the issue, emphasising the pivotal role education plays in effecting social change. This challenge transcends STEM fields, reflecting broader societal issues.

It has been identified that there is a lack of appropriate support or family support leaves for raising and having children. This is a significant obstacle for women seeking to establish and sustain careers in STEM. Primarily, it poses challenges for women aiming to re-enter the workforce after maternity leave. There is a perceived discrepancy in the pace of technological advancements, potentially resulting in a larger knowledge gap compared to other professions, which could impede seamless career re-entry. Secondly, continuous access to childcare services emerged as a critical concern for women who have already resumed their careers. This lack of consistent childcare provision is seen as a catalyst for career interruptions and subsequent dropouts from STEM fields.

Additionally, the absence of gender quotas in key leadership positions hampers women's progress in Board of Director and senior executive roles, perpetuating the gender gap in these sectors. The higher scores in learners/trainees and training VET categories suggest that addressing the gender gap in the digital field is seen as a more significant challenge during training and vocational education. This highlights the importance of targeted initiatives to encourage women to pursue and stay in digital careers.

The equality issue also affects **Vocational Education and Training** in several ways. Firstly, the shortage of women in this field leads to a reduced pool of talent, limiting the diversity of perspectives within the industry. This not only hampers inclusivity of digital tech, but also diminishes the potential for varied ideas and innovation. Moreover, the dearth of female representation contributes to an environment marked by hostility and unnecessary competition. A lack of gender diversity can lead to a homogenous and less collaborative atmosphere, hindering the collective progress of the digital tech sector.

For **Industry**, it is apparent how the impact can be felt, in which an overall lack of diversity in the industry leads to a broader deficit in incorporating various perspectives. Without a diverse workforce, inclusivity is compromised, hindering the industry's ability to address a wide range of user needs and perspectives.

3.4 Identified actions for addressing challenges

3.4.1 Overview of proposed actions by type

In the second phase of the workshop, teams were asked to propose specific action to address the explored challenge. From the proposed actions, the teams selected the top five actions and assessed them against an effort-impact matrix.⁷

For the actions, there were four principal categories identified:

- Programmes - Actions that have a defined set of activities and outputs that can be funded directly or stimulated through public funding or suitable private investment
- Policy and Regulation - Actions which are targeted at policymakers at both European and Member State level. These refer to the coordinated efforts in harmonisation, regulation and incentivisation.
- Infrastructure – Actions that are primarily related to financing the provision of intangible but practical elements across Europe that includes guidelines, tools and networks.
- Communication and Awareness – Delivery of specific campaigns that drive awareness and stimulate change among target populations.

The list of actions per challenge, the assigned impact/effort score and categorisation are provided as tables in **Annex 5**.

It was observed that across all actions provided, there was on average a higher impact/effort coefficient anticipated for actions that provided funding for positions directly, development of guidelines and tools and the development of new courses.

Figure 6. Relative mapping of average impact vs effort per action sub-type

Overall, the participants believed that programmes and communications actions will provide the higher impact for lower effort, at a ratio of 1.3 and 1.1 respectively. All four were above

⁷ Note that for Challenge 3 and Challenge 5 there were two teams assign to each, consequently 10 actions are returned per challenge.

the 1:1 ratio of impact to effort. Looking more detailed, however, it can be seen that certain actions provide a higher return. Among the mapped actions, there are 4 quick wins, 8 projects and 3 strategic actions to review. Outside of these are actions that are low impact or high effort and are provided in the following sections below.

Figure 7. Mapping of each identified action for impact versus effort to provide a clustering of priority actions. Label colours refer to the challenge for which they were identified.

This only reflects the relative mapping performed within each challenge team and is indicative in nature. This means that while we provide in this report a prioritisation, further investigation should be performed to provide more accurate representation of the impact or effort of a specific action, particularly those with an impact score above 3.

For example, those actors in HEI, and from the experiences of the SPECIALISED Masters’ programmes, it has been consistently reported that the accreditation system and associated administrative timelines and burden are a barrier to responding to the evolving needs for ADS. This balance between agility and quality control is difficult, which is why it is unexpected that the 2-3 actions related increasing this flexibility are only expected to result in a conservative impact score of 3.

Quick Wins

Characterised by their relative moderate impact for low effort and include:

CHALLENGE	TYPE	SUB TYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	I	E
2. Accessing the expertise for skilling – the bottleneck in developing the advanced digital talent pool	Programme	Capacity Building	Advanced Skills Course Expansion	Building upon and updating existing courses with new advanced skills tracks alongside developing new courses.	3	2

2. Accessing the expertise for skilling – the bottleneck in developing the advanced digital talent pool	Infrastructure	Guidelines	Pre-BA/MSC Curricular Integration	Providing guidelines for restructuring curricula to include digital skills prior to BA/MSC level education.	4	2
3. Addressing SMEs	Programme	Courses	Bite-Size Training Solutions	Provision of bite-size training and tech solutions to learners.	4	2
5. The need for domain expertise and sectoral divergence in demands	Policy & Regulation	Incentivisation	Private Resource Pooling	Pooling private resources for sectoral interests to enhance educational outcomes.	3	2

For the action Advanced Skills Course Expansion, this is assumed to be the same as that provided for Integrated ADS University Courses resulting from the Challenge 1. Rate of tech development and convergence, although in this case the relative impact and effort was poorer: Impact: 3, Effort: 5.

Strategic

The actions are those high effort, high reward actions that require significant effort by policy makers over the longer term. These include:

CHALLENGE	TYPE	TYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	I	E
1. Rate of tech development and convergence – skills fit for industry	Infrastructure	Tools	European Skills Gap Initiative	Establishment of a European-level effort to quickly define and address skills gaps.	5	5
5. The need for domain expertise and sectoral divergence in demands	Programme	Scholarships	Erasmus Professional Mobility	Implementing Erasmus for professional mobility to facilitate cross-border learning opportunities.	5	5
6. The leaky pipeline of women in digital	Policy & Regulation	Other	Childcare Policy Advocacy	Advocacy for policy change in childcare to support educational access.	5	4

On the action European Skills Gap Initiative, it is worth noting that the current Work Programme for DIGITAL, is implementing the Data Spaces for Skills which should provide the infrastructure required to perform such actions.⁸ Concurrently, CEDEFOP with Eurostat provides an analysis of job postings in 32 countries through their Skills-OVATE project.⁹

Projects

These actions are high impact with moderate effort and are numerous across the challenges. They are actions that can be delivered in the mid-term and have a certain level of uncertainty over results as with all projects. These include:

⁸ DIGITAL-2024-CLOUD-DATA-06-SKILLS

⁹ <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/skills-online-vacancies>

CHALLENGE	TYPE	SUB TYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	I	E
1. Rate of tech development and convergence – skills fit for industry	Programme	Capacity Building	Content Validation Process	Validation of content by students, faculties, and external stakeholders.	5	3
3. Addressing SMEs	Infrastructure	Tools	Education Opportunity Platform	Creation of a One-stop shop platform for educational opportunities.	4	3
3. Addressing SMEs	Programme	Courses	Executive ADS Education	Education for HR & CEOs, emphasising the importance of ADS for strategic decision-making.	5	3
4. Finding candidates at the right level - the supply of candidates for very advanced programmes	Infrastructure	Tools	Candidate Engagement Pathways	Design of DSJP learning paths to attract and engage potential candidates.	4	3
4. Finding candidates at the right level - the supply of candidates for very advanced programmes	Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	Unified Competency Assessment	Application of unified competency portfolios for comprehensive assessment.	5	3
4. Finding candidates at the right level - the supply of candidates for very advanced programmes	Communications and awareness	Communications and awareness	Role Model Promotion	Promotion of educational programmes by role models to inspire participation.	5	3
6. The leaky pipeline of women in digital	Programme	Courses	Tech Workshops for Girls	Conducting regular workshops for girls in the school curriculum to foster tech interest.	4	3
6. The leaky pipeline of women in digital	Programme	Capacity Building	Teacher In-Service Training	Provision of in-service training for teachers to stay updated on career choices and new roles.	5	3

4 KEY LEARNINGS IN DELIVERING ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS

4.1 Identifying demand for course design

The advancement of projects focusing on the delivery of Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) varies across distinct stages. While some initiatives are in the preliminary phases of planning and designing their courses, others have progressed to actively delivering skills in their selected formats.

Critical to the success of any project is during the initial phase of design—the assessment and identification of demand.¹⁰ Success in this phase is not solely dependent on identifying the specific technology areas in demand but also on identifying the sectoral and industrial connections that may arise to ensure that the potential programme can offer learning options that **enable students not only to acquire the right skills, but also to ensure that they can apply them in the right context.**

In the approaches taken, **one project might choose the external assessment of labour market demand, gaps in the provision and demand and industry sentiment** on what profiles are and will be lacking in the future through consultations. Others emerge out of **research projects where a specific need in a specific industry already has been identified**, which then allows

The REBOOT SKILLS project, can be traced back to a collaborative effort within an ecosystem of a research project related to the digitalisation of manufacturing processes. This training demand emerged with the objective of providing research-driven training tailored to the needs of the industry.

the projects to tailor their action very specifically from the start to the identified target group. Finally, a **combination approach may be taken within already existing and identified fields with emerging societal topics**, such as when it comes to in the example of growing legal and ethical considerations in the field of AI.

Regardless of the method, however, the **fast rate of tech development presents a potential barrier when it comes to the effective assessment of demand.** Technologies evolve quickly, leading to a dynamic job market with rapidly changing skill requirements.

Identifying the specific skills in demand becomes challenging as these **requirements may shift before a programme is developed and launched.** The fast-paced nature of technology development can create a gap between industry needs and the skills taught in academic programmes. This gap may result in graduates lacking some of the latest and most sought-after skills, impacting their competitiveness in the job market and the success of the programme.

¹⁰ The identification of demand and such research should form part of the preliminary design and definition of a joint programme with consequences for the partnership formation, financial sustainability and strategic direction of funded activities.

Having **strong partnerships with businesses and aligning instructional methodologies with real-world applications are pivotal** to ensure the practical relevance of the imparted skills, as well as to adequately prepare students for the demands and applicability within the industry. This can happen through different types of measures such as summer schools where industry lecturers provide the possibility for students to learn the application of their skills or just by having a certain share of industry lecturers generally.

Developing close relationships and actively engaging with SMEs offer significant advantages in aligning skills with industry needs, despite the **practical challenges arising from intense competition for leading talent between academia and industry when implementing these partnerships**. Issues have arisen in securing industry lecturers, particularly in specialised technology domains like cybersecurity, and in finding professionals willing to commit for extended periods.

Furthermore, **university structures, with fixed staff numbers and salary structures, pose additional barriers to efficiently engaging industry professionals** as lecturers.

The inflexible structures within these institutions often demand imaginative solutions when designing the practical elements of the programme. Introducing evening lectures to cater to the specific needs of professionals, who are the target audience for these programmes, might not align with the standard procedures and may require specific approvals.

Moreover, it is pivotal **to offer adaptable learning options**. This doesn't just involve diverse instructional delivery methods but also entails **granting students the autonomy to chart their educational paths based on their experiences, skills, and personal interests**. This approach not only cultivates a more customised and immersive learning environment but also nurtures a sense of ownership and motivation among students. Primarily delivering online lectures to ensure flexibility for students, while incorporating tailored initiatives for face-to-face engagement, has proven to be an effective strategy.

Additional barriers are rooted within the diverse structures and formats of current education programmes, necessitating concerted efforts in developing joint initiatives and finding that common level. This collaboration may encounter challenges due to potential inflexibility within the internal processes of these collaborating institutions. Starting from a common ground and then relying on creativity and pragmatism has been a recommended approach. Finding synergies between the institutions has also been presented as a priority and potential barrier to overcome. It's not obvious from the very beginning which types of synergies can be encountered and implemented in concern with for example repeated and regular mobility of teaching staff or the sharing of course content and material.

DIS4SME training modules on location data interoperability primarily draw upon a collection of practical business case studies. These case studies are meticulously crafted to address real-world challenges closely aligned with the business sectors encompassed by the European Union's Common Data Spaces initiative.

4.2 Building for sustainability and scale

In this context, sustainability embodies a multifaceted concept. The foremost concern relates to securing funding beyond the official project end. Within the projects period, projects are supported by the Digital Europe Programme at a rate of 50% of all total eligible costs. Consequently, it is crucial for projects to think of ways to ensure comprehensive financing and to guarantee the continuity of actions implemented during the funding period beyond the

project's end. There are various ways to design a business model and ensure the financial sustainability of the programmes. Concretely, there have been mentioned 4 principal models to approach this issue:

1. Introducing tuition fees
2. Attracting sponsorship from industry
3. Introducing complementary revenue streams, e.g operation of a consulting division
4. Follow-on public funding

Furthermore, smaller solutions like licensing course materials can offer another source for funding, particularly considering the recognition **that maintaining up-to-date material is a particular challenge** to be considered when assessing the sustainability strategy.

There are specific barriers when it comes to some of these funding approaches. Most prominently discussed has been the introduction of tuition fees. **Not all universities permit this practice, and some might have prerequisites, creating unique hurdles for joint programmes.** Moreover, the introduction of tuition fees could potentially influence students'

AI and Health, a Specialised project focusing on AI applications for healthcare, was presenting three different alternative opportunities for funding, the ERASMUS+ KA131, investment in other projects launched locally as part of the National Future Investment programme and lectures for the general public of the Université du Temps Libre.

willingness to apply, particularly impacting key target groups, as some students might be sponsored by companies while others are not.

Next to the financial sustainability the area of partnerships and collaboration must be considered. The continuation of the programmes very much relies on the **continuation of the partnerships and collaboration in between the institutions of the established consortium.** Closely related to this issue is the layer of sustainability, which is

related to the actuality of the programme, especially considering the fast development of technology. It is these close partnerships with industry and SMEs that can help staying on top of the current developments and their applications in the business context. An **industry advisory board is only one way to establish this collaboration in a structured manner.** The European Digital Innovation Hubs, providing support to companies and public sector organisations can also support the feedback loop in this matter. Being flexible and reacting to the latest developments is crucial but at the same time resource intensive, so it is important to facet this issue in a structured way.

Accreditation can be essential in ensuring the sustainability of a programme, and a lack thereof can threaten this. However, in its absence, **developing a strong reputation holds significant importance, particularly for programmes that lack official recognition,** such as certain professional Master's programmes. It's crucial to engage with alumni and gather testimonials, alongside employing credentials to establish comparability with other programmes and validate a programme's quality, thereby enhancing its credibility.

Concluding, the different facets of sustainability of the programmes are key issues that need to be addressed from the very beginning of the projects, possibly even in the Grant Agreement, to ensure that actions funded not only fulfil the promised impact go beyond that – **it is not solely about ensuring the continuation of the educational programme but also about boosting its impact.**

5 CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Addressing the specifics of Advanced Digital Skills in the Digital Decade

The stimulation of supply and ensuring the relevance of Advanced Digital Skills initiative requires a multipronged approach. Currently, there is an emphasis on HEIs as the principal stakeholder for the development and delivery of such courses, however, there is an evident demand for this to be developed closely with industry and with training partners who are closer to industry. From within the exploration of all six challenges, it was found that HEIs are facing significant constraints in their own access to the talent and technology. It is observed that there is an ongoing need for industry to engage with HEI but also for HEI and VET to coordinate better.

The rate of technology development and adoption presents a significant challenge across all stakeholders and is having an effect on the capacity to respond. There is a call for greater sharing of frameworks and data to overcome this and enable more fluid communications across stakeholders and support targeted investments. This also drives a demand for support in defining those competence frameworks and providing that certainty on what is the ‘fuzzy end’ of future digital technology demands.

5.2 Supporting European Industry

One of the main causes behind the lack of investment and uptake of advanced digital skills training and initiatives is linked to the defined return on investment. This takes many forms from the lack of visibility present among senior staff, to the uncertain nature of future demands. The business case must be made and there is a role for enabling key persons within industry to build that business case.

It is believed that actions that drive awareness, provide sensitisation and equip decision makers with the right set of data and knowledge will lead to a greater appetite for investment from companies, but this is very challenging in the resource limited confines of an SME. The role of intermediaries such as associations, networks and platforms are seen as necessary to communicate between the tech development community, industry, policy and education and training. This, however, does not remove the need for direct lines of communication between businesses and policy or businesses and education.

5.3 Priorities for actions

There is a mix of actions proposed across programmes, infrastructure and policy. There is a specific need for the development of the intangible infrastructure to support both companies and education and training providers. Aside from the direct financing of capacity-building programme and courses, it is evident that a common set of tools, guidelines and shared data will be key to unlocking the speed of quality talent development.

This includes the fostering of stronger networks and clusters across stakeholders to provide the structured mechanisms for collaboration and joint action while eliminating blind spots. Some solutions are already being addressed through the various EU funded programmes, however, this visibility is not reaching even the members ‘Brussels Bubble’.

Actions related to role models are seen as important to providing the necessary flow of talent, but there are specific actions needed to give HEIs better access to this talent both as teachers and as students.

5.4 A call for coordinated mission from policy

As evident from above, providing an accelerated development of ADS among European learners and workers, is highly dependent on multiple areas of strategy and policy. Harmonisation of processes and guidelines across the whole the EU is required to remove barriers to organisations and ensure that effective collaboration across MS can occur within the required timeframe for 2030.

More directly, it was observed that while the DIGITAL programme is investing in the ADS talent required for improving the competitiveness of European digital supply chains, it requires a ‘whole of policy’ approach. That is to say that there is an evident lack of coherence between related skills and education initiatives delivered under ERASMUS, ESF, ERDF, Horizon and DIGITAL, operating in silos and consequently, limiting the scale and speed of impact that can be achieved.

5.5 Women in Digital – a systemic issue?

Among all challenges discussed, the Women in Digital challenge was singled out for having a set of causes that are considered systemic. These related to the nature of the ICT industry, the perceptions of it and practical difficulties relating to contextual elements like access to childcare and compatibility of career paths.

Addressing the gender gap in ICT Specialists has a problem where the career and conditions, in spite of objectively good employment opportunities, are not proving a sufficient pull factor. On the other hand, the lower supply of girls from primary and secondary education of potential candidates for IT training and education is not progressing at a sufficient approach.

For actions to be taken, it must be from both ends, while recognising the social context and pervasive cultural biases. This requires a demonstrated attractiveness and welcoming environment from the digital industry, anecdotally referred to as actively hostile.¹¹ At the same time actions to improve the capacity of teachers and close gaps in gendered learning and access to STEM subjects.

5.6 Ensuring the success and sustainability of programme investments

It was accepted that all funded actions, by their frontier nature need to prepare participants for an uncertain future. This implies a level of risk and venture in the definition and development of both courses and content.

Successful initiatives benefit from starting from a well-developed base, either through market research into requirements or from existing experience and assets developed within

¹¹ For reference, it is anecdotally report that women are significantly more criticised for their contributions in open source communities or openly receive abuse in gaming communities.

collaborative research environments. Each programme, while sharing common characteristics will be unique in terms of scope, participants and methods.

Fundamentally, any programme or course developed must, prior to making significant investment, ensure there is sufficient demand, an active population and a sound business model. This foundation can be explored and experimented with during received funding phases but any actions must work towards a strategic lifetime approach. This includes accounting for the expiration of content and the restructuring of delivery partnerships.

ANNEX 1 – WORKSHOP AGENDA

AGENDA

DIGITAL EUROPE PROGRAMME PROJECTS MEETING – Advanced digital skills

In person

24.10.2023 9:30-16:30 CET
 Meeting room – 2.C (Second floor)
 Centre Albert Borschette
 Rue Froissart 36
 1049 Brussels

Participants

- EC; DG CNECT, HaDEA
- LEADS CSA
- CEF-Funded Projects – [Masters in AI](#) (4)
- SPECIALISED [First call](#) (6)
- [Short term training courses](#) (9)
- SPECIALISED [Second Call](#) (4)
- Linked initiatives: Digital skills and jobs platform ([DSJP](#)), [EmpowerED](#), [DS4Skills](#)

Purpose

The purpose of the meeting is to reflect and take stock of the achievements of the ongoing DEP projects in the field of Advanced digital skills, on lessons learned, gaps in achievements as well as promising elements, and potential recommendations. Furthermore, you will have the possibility to contribute to the exploratory work on future policy actions and funding needs to close the digital skills gap and to reach the 20 million ICT specialists employed in the EU by 2030 as well as on how to ensure the sustainability of the initiatives beyond the funding period.

Finally, you will have many networking opportunities to maximise synergies between projects and define concrete actions for collaboration and a joint working agenda for the coming months.

Agenda

	SESSION
9:30	Welcome and Scene Setting Rehana Schwininger-Ladak, Head of Unit, DG CNECT, Unit G.2, Interactive Technologies, Digital for Culture and Education Brendan Rowan, LEADS CSA
10:00	ROUND TABLE Increasing Impact – Meeting the Needs of the Digital Decade Open discussion on the key areas of Advanced digital skills that are required for the Digital Europe Programme Tanya Suárez, LEADS CSA (Moderator) Asja Satler, DG CNECT, Unit G.2 Finbarr Feeney, Human Centered AI Masters Ilker Demirkol, MERIT Minna Isomursu, REBOOT SKILLS
11:00	Coffee Break

AGENDA

11:30	WORKSHOP Policy actions and opportunities
13:00	Best practices and collaboration request (pitches) Horacio González-Vélez, DIGITAL4Business Milva Carbonaro, DIS4SME Chiara Demartini, xAIM
13:30	Lunch break
14:30	Best practices and collaboration request (pitches) Christel Dupont-Ferrier and Christophe Dubois, AI and Health Pambos Pantziaros, EAGLE Tomislava Recheva, DSJP
15:00	ROUND TABLE Generating greater sustainability of actions – strategies and opportunities Oscar Rodriguez Diaz, Project Advisor, HaDEA, Unit B.2.1 Digital Europe Programme (Moderator) Claudio Feijóo, AI4Gov Maria do Carmo Gomes, ManagiDiTH Christos Douligeris, CyberSecPro Christos Karras, TRUST-FOOD
16:00	Summary, takeaways and next steps Rehana Schwinniger-Ladak, Head of Unit, DG CNECT, Unit G.2

ANNEX 2: FUNDED ACTIONS FOR REACHING THE DIGITAL DECADE TARGETS

In the first 4 years of the DIGITAL Programme, the following project clusters have been/were proposed to be financed:

- Specialised education programmes – increasing and improving the offer of education programmes and the number of students specialised in key capacity areas, such as AI, data, cybersecurity, IoT, blockchain, robotics and quantum.
- Advanced Digital Skills analysis - supporting the rollout of initiatives for advanced digital skills development, by gathering inputs on the existing education offers in digital areas and the related needs of the labour market.
- Short term training courses - giving the possibility to the current workforce to access trainings reflecting the latest developments in key capacity areas, such as quantum, Cybersecurity, AI and other emerging technologies.
- Other training initiatives – such as reinforcing skills in semiconductors, the cybersecurity skills academy and boosting digital skills of young people.
- Supporting initiatives –such as the Digital Skills and Jobs Platform together with the National Coalitions, the HPC training platform and support to the International HPC Summer School, traineeships as the HPC virtual training academy, a and the coordination and support actions to promote European innovation in education and Girls and Women in Digital.

In addition to the above, the four Master’s in AI actions were funded prior to the DIGITAL programme, under the Connecting Europe Facility, and form part of the project cluster¹². The figure below provides an overview of principal actions contained within the ADS Cluster.

Figure 8. Overview of the funded courses and programmes under the ADS pillar of the DIGITAL Programme and CEF-Digital as of 31st October 2023.

¹² [Universities, SMEs and researches join forces to deliver new Master courses in AI | Shaping Europe’s digital future \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu)

SPECIALISED MASTER'S PROGRAMMES

Funded programmes are expected to deliver a tertiary degree education programme addressing the topics like data, IoT, AI, blockchain, cybersecurity, and quantum.

Funded actions provide partners with a means for cross-border collaboration and sharing of expertise, resources, facilities, and staff while promoting cross-sector mobility between Higher Education Institutions and private sector organisations. Initiatives will be financed for 48 months to a total of 20 million EUR, of which 50% is provided by the DIGITAL Programme. Examples of projects include:

- MERIT – developing a joint Master's programme that addresses the market needs in Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things, and Cybersecurity.
- DS4Health – developing an international Master's programme in digital health, focusing on key areas such as Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, data, Robotics, and the Internet of Things.
- DigiQ – upgrading existing quantum Technology Master's programmes, developing new programmes, and providing a bridging programme to align non-specialist degrees with the needs of the QT workforce.

SHORT-TERM TRAINING PROGRAMMES

Funded programmes will deliver short-term training courses in advanced technologies for both people already in employment and jobseekers.

Initiatives are expected to be financed for 36 months to a total of 25 million EUR, of which 75% is co-funded for SMEs and 50% for all the other beneficiaries, is provided by the DIGITAL Programme. Examples of projects include:

- REBOOT Skills – delivering 25 free-of-charge courses to employees of manufacturing industry SMEs or unemployed people wishing to find employment in the manufacturing industry.
- SME4DD – delivering short-term training programmes in the areas of AI, blockchain and Cybersecurity, based on the needs of companies – especially SMEs.
- CloudCamp - Cloud Training Program exclusively SMEs to facilitate their digital transformation efforts.

SPECIALISED ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS ANALYSIS

Funded Coordination and Support Actions are expected to provide an analysis of the labour market needs and recommended priority areas for investment and give indications on the most appropriate delivery modes for training.

The currently funded action is Leading Europe's Advanced Digital Skills (LEADS) which detects the main trends in emerging skills needs per technology area and defines the gap in the provision and demand of education and training. Additionally, LEADS develops guidelines for new approaches to course development, companywide practices and talent pipeline development. The project provides insights to create an ecosystem between education institutions and companies.

TARGETTED PROGRAMMES, NETWORKS, AND CLUSTERS

Reinforcing Skills in semiconductors focuses on developing a European semiconductors skill academy: a European network of higher education institutions and relevant industries, including start-ups and SMEs in microelectronics. Additionally, it includes the definition of a platform among Vocational and Educational Training centres, industry, academia and social partners to address the need of continuing vocational training to enhance employability.

CYBERSECURITY SKILLS ACADEMY

The Cybersecurity Skills Academy focuses on boosting digital skills of young people, in particular girls is focusing on increasing the number of students pursuing digital studies and careers, with a special focus on increasing participation of girls. It will support joint actions between leading technical higher education institutions, businesses and schools to promote digital studies, through hands-on activities and challenge-based projects. The selected training will also manage the EU code week.

OTHER INITIATIVES

DIGITAL SKILLS AND JOBS PLATFORM

The DSJP serves as the primary hub for information and services related to digital skills in the EU. It offers access to training, career development support, good practices, expert advice, tools and resources, data, funding opportunities and financial instruments. It is a collaborative space where Community members can network, interact, and grow. This action funds further development of the quality of content and services available on the DSJP and its interoperability.

PROMOTING EUROPEAN INNOVATION IN EDUCATION

The project supported closer collaboration in the digital education sector in Europe amongst European EdTech start-ups/SMEs and other relevant stakeholders and across Europe. It fostered the exchange of good practices at pan-European level, aiming at increased capacities of the national education systems and at distance, innovative, effective, and inclusive learning.

ANNEX 3 – PROJECT BROCHURE

ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS
 DIGITAL EUROPE PROGRAMME

Funded by the European Union

DIGITAL EUROPE PROGRAMME PROJECTS MEETING

PROJECT BROCHURE

Brussels
24th October 2023

ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS IN THE DIGITAL PROGRAMME

Strategic Objective 4

"Advanced Digital Skills shall support the development of advanced digital skills in areas covered by the Programme in order to contribute to increasing Europe's talent pool, bridge the digital divide and foster greater professionalism, especially with regard to high performance and cloud computing, big data analytics, cybersecurity, distributed ledger technologies, quantum technologies, robotics, AI, while taking gender balance into account."

REGULATION (EU) 2021/694

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 2

ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS PROJECTS OVERVIEW

CEP Funded Projects – Masters in AI

Short-term training courses

SPECIALISED First Call

SPECIALISED Second Call

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

LEADS

Leading Europe's Advanced Digital Skills

advancedskills.eu

Start date: 01/10/2022
End date: 30/03/2024

Coordinator
BluSpecs

Description

LEADS delivers insights into the changing Advanced Digital Skills demands within a dynamic technological development context to equip the education and training communities by providing roadmaps and guidelines. It supports the delivery of the DIGITAL programme through working closely with industries for the uptake of training, reskilling, and upskilling the workforce and communities and supports the delivery of the SPECIALISED education programmes with cross-project structures for increasing the success across the whole initiative.

- Attendees**
- Tanya Suarez, BluSpecs
 - Brendan Rowan, BluSpecs
 - Max Welford, BluSpecs
 - Nina Blessing, BluSpecs
 - Eugenia Kyriotis, Martel
 - Shirley Kavanagh, Trinity College Dublin
 - Spiros Borotis, Maggioli
 - Juan José Moreno Navarro, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
 - Simona Romeo, AIOTI

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 4

CEF-Funded Projects – Masters in AI

AI4GOV

Master on AI for public services

www.ai4gov-hub.eu/

Start date: 01/04/2021
End date: 01/06/2024

Description

This Master's programme targets the development of advanced digital skills in the public services sector to address its lack of highly specialised digital skills in AI. Participants are awarded a joint master degree from Technical University of Madrid and Polytechnic University of Milan on "AI for public services". After completing the joint programme, students will get the opportunity to study an additional year at Tallinn University of Technology to receive a MSc degree in e-Government Technologies and Services.

- Coordinator**
- Technical University of Madrid
- Attendees**
- Claudio Feijóo, Technical University of Madrid

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 5

CEF-Funded Projects – Masters in AI

MAI4CAREU

Master in AI for Careers in EU

mai4car.eu

Start date: 01/06/2021
End date: 31/05/2024

Description

Master's Programme in Artificial Intelligence will train students in the latest AI developments and applications. The aim is to deliver a modern programme, containing a strong interdisciplinary element as required by modern human-centric, explainable, and responsible artificial intelligence. The compulsory programme includes courses on artificial intelligence and ethics, as well as on artificial intelligence and entrepreneurship, and AI on the edge webinars. Providing career counselling to students is a high priority, with the objective of helping all graduates to successfully pursue an AI-related career, possibly set up their own start-ups.

- Coordinator**
- University of Cyprus
- Attendees**
- George Kirkos, CYENS Centre of Excellence in Cyprus

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 7

CEF-Funded Projects – Masters in AI

HCAIM

Human Centered AI Master

humancentered-ai.eu

Start date: 01/01/2021
End date: 31/12/2023

Description

The HCAIM programme has been built to train professionals in the field as socially-responsible and ethically aware AI architects. In particular, these architects pay attention to the responsible application of AI, in line with the vision of the European Union. It was developed by a Consortium of three excellence centres, three SMEs and four Universities. The partnership brings together professionals from the world of academia and companies with considerable records of interest in the human-centred and ethical aspects of AI.

- Coordinator**
- Technological University of Dublin
- Attendees**
- Finbarr Feeney, Technological University of Dublin

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 6

CEF-Funded Projects – Masters in AI

xAIM

eXplainable Artificial Intelligence in healthcare Management

xaim.eu

Start date: 01/05/2021
End date: 31/10/2024

Description

xAIM is an online Master programme aiming to create an interdisciplinary environment where students are trained to work at the intersection of Data Science, AI and Healthcare. Students will learn the fundamentals of Machine Learning and Data Science so that they can handle and analyse large, heterogeneous and complex datasets representative of the healthcare sector. It has been developed by 4 Universities: the University of Pavia, the Goethe University (Germany), Keele University (UK), Leibniz University Hannover (Germany) and the University of Ljubljana (Slovenia).

- Coordinator**
- University of Pavia
- Attendees**
- Maria Chiara Demartini, University of Pavia
 - Valentina Beretta, University of Pavia

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 8

SPECIALISED First Call

AI and Health

Advanced digital skills programme Artificial Intelligence and Health

univ-
amu.fr/en/public/advanced-digital-skills-ai-health

Start date: 01/12/2022
End date: 30/11/2026

Description

The demand for training in Artificial Intelligence applications for health is increasing among healthcare practitioners and stakeholders in biomedical research. The Advanced Digital Skills program, AI and Health, offers five types of training: a joint curriculum, two MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses), Workshop on digital technologies, three short-term courses for professionals, recorded conferences.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aix-Marseille University | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christophe Dubois, Aix-Marseille University Christel Dupont-Ferrier, Aix-Marseille University |
|--|--|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 9

SPECIALISED First Call

CyberSecPro

Collaborative, Multi-modal and Agile Professional Cybersecurity Training Program for A Skilled Workforce In The European Digital Single Market and Industries

www.cybersecpro-project.eu

Start date: 01/12/2022
End date: 30/11/2025

Description

14 HEIs and thirteen security companies from 16 EU countries are designing the agile CyberSecPro professional cybersecurity training programme. CyberSecPro complements and enhances existing academic programmes by fostering collaboration between innovation, research, industry, academia, and SMEs. It provides practical and hands-on training, bridging the divide between degrees, real-world work, and marketable cybersecurity skill sets. The goal is for CyberSecPro to become the best practice model for all cybersecurity training programs, aligning with the digitalisation efforts and industry demands.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Johann Wolfgang Goethe Universität Frankfurt am Main | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christos Douligeris, University of Piraeus Foteini Markella Petropoulou, Zelus |
|--|---|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 10

SPECIALISED First Call

DIGITAL4Business

Master's Programme focused on the practical application of Advanced Digital Skills within European Companies

digital4business.eu

Start date: 01/12/2022
End date: 30/11/2026

Description

The DIGITAL4Business European Master's Programme aims to create an innovative and sustainable European Master's Programme in Advanced Digital Skills. This programme brings together higher education institutions, research centres, employment services, and industry to design and deliver a market-driven academic curriculum focused on the practical application of advanced digital skills in European businesses. The courses cover topics like AI, cybersecurity, and the cloud, addressing the skill needs of SMEs and companies to enhance their competitiveness and growth.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National College of Ireland | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horacio González-Vélez, National College of Ireland Brian Cochrane, Schuman Associates |
|---|---|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 11

SPECIALISED First Call

DigiQ

DigiQ: Digitally Enhanced European Quantum Technology Master

www.digiq.eu

Start date: 01/10/2022
End date: 30/09/2026

Description

To meet the growing demand for a quantum-ready workforce, the DigiQ project aims to transform the educational ecosystem in Quantum Technology (QT). By introducing innovative teaching methods and a multinational program structure, the project seeks to scale up and enhance quantum education across the European Higher Education Area. This involves upgrading existing QT Master programs, developing new programs, and providing a bridging program to align non-specialist degrees with the needs of the QT workforce.

- | | |
|---|-------------------------|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aarhus University | <p>Attendees</p> |
|---|-------------------------|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 12

SPECIALISED First Call

DIGITWIN4CIUE

Digital Twins For Complex Infrastructures And Urban Ecosystems

digitwin4ciue.eu

Start date: 01/11/2022
End date: 31/10/2026

Description

The project prepares and delivers a comprehensive master's programme on Digital Twins for Complex Infrastructures and Urban ecosystems, specifically targeting civil engineers working in strategic areas like transport, cities, energy, water, and the environment. The master's programme will have a duration of one year, offering a blended learning approach that is international, executive, and professional. Its main focus will be on providing training in relevant digital skills required for digital twins in infrastructures, such as IoT, AI, and data analytics.

- | | |
|--|------------------|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical University of Madrid | |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 13

SPECIALISED First Call

DS4Health

Digital skills for Healthcare Transformation

digital-skills-jobs.europa.eu/en/ds4health

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2026

Description

DS4Health develops and implements an international Master's programme in digital health, focusing on key areas such as Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, Data, Robotics, and the Internet of Things. The programme enhances higher education for healthcare professionals by deepening their understanding and skills in the design, use, and development of digital technologies. With a citizen-centred approach and emphasis on soft skills and entrepreneurship, DS4Health addresses societal challenges outlined in the European Pillar of Social Rights and Sustainable Development Goals.

- | | |
|--|--|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aachen University Hospital | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joyce Kao, Aachen University Hospital Gernot Marx, Aachen University Hospital |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 14

SPECIALISED First Call

ManagiDiTH

Master of Managing Digital Transformation in the Health Sector

managidith.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2026

Description

This interdisciplinary programme equips professionals with the necessary capacity to address complex healthcare challenges in ageing societies. By fostering a co-creation process, an ecosystem will be built to collaboratively find innovative solutions. The programme's effectiveness relies on a combination of transversal skills (communication, management, social, and research), sector-specific knowledge (healthcare), service design, and technological learning. The programme brings together four partner universities, a research centre, and relevant healthcare and technology organizations.

- | | |
|--|--|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Iscte - University Institute of Lisbon | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maria do Carmo Gomes, Iscte - University Institute of Lisbon |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 15

SPECIALISED First Call

MERIT

Master of Science in Smart, Secure and Interconnected Systems

Start date: 01/10/2022
End date: 30/09/2026

Description

The MERIT project creates an educational ecosystem for training digital specialists by bringing together universities, industry partners, research centres, and technology organisations. The project focuses on the design of a joint Master's programme that addresses the market needs in Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things, and Cybersecurity. The programme will offer a high-quality and flexible career path with mobility opportunities, blended learning options, research integration, and support for students' career development.

- | | |
|---|---|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical University of Catalunya | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ilker Demirkol, Technical University of Catalunya Simona Ramanauskaitė, Vilnius Gediminas Technical University |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 16

Short term training courses

BioNT

BIO Network for Training

biont-training.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/03/2026

Description

BIO Network for Training provides a training programme and community for digital skills relevant to the biotechnology industry and biomedical sector. The basic curriculum includes handling, processing and visualizing biological data and/or the usage of computational biology tools, while the advanced curriculum aims at professionalising Life Sciences data management, processing and analysis skills.

- | | |
|---|------------------|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Molecular Biology Laboratory | |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 17

Short term training courses

CYRUS

A personalised, customised, work-based training framework for enhanced CyBeR-security skills across indUstrial Sectors

research.dblue.it/cyrus-project

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

The project provides training on cybersecurity for transport and manufacturing organisations. A complete set of skills and measures to be vigilant to identify and respond to cyber-attacks will be delivered within the CYRUS framework. Virtualisation, dedicated cyber-range simulations in operational settings, and work-based learning will allow timely and efficient course delivery.

- | | |
|---|---|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deep Blue | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bhavesh Sharma, Deep Blue Nicola Cavagnetto, Deep Blue |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 19

Short term training courses

CloudCamp4SMEs

CloudCamp4SMEs – Empowering the digital transformation of European SMEs

spaces.fundingbox.com/c/cloudcamp4smes

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

CloudCamp4SMEs (CC4SMEs) empowers the digital transformation of EU SMEs by facilitating access to high-quality, low-cost training courses focusing on high-demand digital skills for Cloud Technologies and based on Cloud solutions and training content developed by global leaders in cloud technology.

- | | |
|--|------------------|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> FundingBox Communities | |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 18

Short term training courses

DigiAdvance

Advancing key digital skill capabilities in the SME Sector

digiadvance.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

The project addresses digital skills gaps, shortages, and mismatches in technology areas such as blockchain, big data, and machine learning, in particular among small and medium-sized (SME) enterprises. DigiAdvance brings together experts from the higher education sector and industry to support the development of advanced digital skills among SME owners, managers, and employees

- | | |
|--|------------------|
| Coordinator | Attendees |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dublin City University | |

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 20

Short term training courses

DIS4SME

Data Interoperability Skills for SMEs

Description

DIS4SME provides SMEs with the right skills required to orient their Digital Transformation strategies and plans around data interoperability. Training providers belong both to Higher education institutions as well as to private sector, to ensure that the training programmes respond to the real needs of SMEs and cover state-of-the-art technological as well as policy trends.

dis4sme.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Coordinator

- GISIG Geographical Information Systems

Attendees

- Milva Carbonaro, GISIG Geographical Information Systems
- Giacomo Martirano, Epsilon Italia

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 21

Short term training courses

EAGLE

CovEring the trAining Gap in digital skills for European SMEs manpowEr

Description

The EAGLE project designs and delivers high-quality specialised training courses (6 courses in total), reflecting the latest developments in key capacity areas (Cybersecurity, Big Data, Robotics Blockchain and Smart Energy), supporting the development of advanced digital skills of people in the labour force, with a focus on SMEs, both for managers and employees

projecteagle.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Coordinator

- University of Burgos

Attendees

- Eduardo Bayona, University of Burgos
- Pambos Pantziaros, Vernian RTI

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 22

Short term training courses

Level Up

LEVEraging knowLEDge of training providers in UPskilling and reskilling of SME managers and employees towards empowering their digital transformation

Description

Level Up empowers the labour force of European SMEs in digital competencies through the development and provision of short-term training courses focusing on cybersecurity, data literacy, data analytics, artificial intelligence, microelectronics/microcontrollers, internet of things, 3D printing and 3D modelling, cloud and programming. Expected reach: 15000 participants from 3000 SMEs.

levelup-skills.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Coordinator

- GrantXpert

Attendees

- Celia Hadjichristodoulou, GrantXpert
- Stephani Theophanous, GrantXpert

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 23

Short term training courses

QTIndu

Quantum Technologies courses for Industry

Description

The objectives of the project are i) the development of the nucleus for a harmonised pan-European end-to-end short-term training programme in quantum technologies for enterprises, ii) training courses specifically tailored to the requirements of companies and SMEs from different business sectors, and iii) the creation and provision of guidelines and routes for a scale up to a comprehensive pan-European scale.

qtindu.eu

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Coordinator

- QURECA Spain

Attendees

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023

1/29/2024 | 24

Short term training courses

REBOOT SKILLS

Rebooting manufacturing industry with digitalisation skill development

oulu.fi/en/projects/rebooting-manufacturing-industry-digitalisation-skill-development

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

Four universities and four professional organisations deliver 25 free-of-charge courses to employees of manufacturing industry SMEs or unemployed people wishing to find an employment in the manufacturing industry. The 25 courses focus on the key capacity areas AI, cybersecurity, robotics, IoT. Expected reach: 1197 participants will be reskilled and upskilled

- | | |
|--|--|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> University of Oulu | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minna Isomursu, University of Oulu |
|--|--|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 25

Short term training courses

Tech Time 2 Skill

Tech Time 2 Skill : fostering the acquisition of the most in-demand advanced digital skills in AI and Cybersecurity by the European labour force

<https://techttime2skill.actoriaf5.org/>

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

Tech Time 2 Skill targets the acquisition of advanced digital skills in AI and Cybersecurity by the European labour force in order to foster the European Union's digital talents pools and support the digital transformation of European SMEs in a sustainable manner. The consortium develops, pilots, and deploys 6 high-quality digital training programmes.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BeCode | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Xavier Ronveaux, BeCode Theo Biddulph, Simplon |
|--|---|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 27

Short term training courses

SME4DD

Training SMEs for the Digital Decade

eitdigital.eu/eu-collaborations/sme4dd

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

Short-term training programmes in three strategic digital technologies for Europe: 1) Artificial Intelligence, 2) Blockchain, 3) Cybersecurity. These training programmes will be designed based on the needs of companies - especially SMEs - and will increase the number of men and women able to design, develop and deploy digital solutions in the economy and across sectors.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EIT Digital | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asja Kamenica, EIT Digital Elia Giovacchini, EIT Digital |
|---|---|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 26

Short term training courses

TRUST FOOD

Advanced Digital Skills on Blockchain for Trusted Food Supply Chains

linkedin.com/company/trustfoodde/

Start date: 01/01/2023
End date: 31/12/2025

Description

Training courses reflecting the latest developments in the area of blockchain technologies applied holistically to the Food Supply Chain will be offered to people in the labour force, with a focus on SMEs, as well as to job seekers.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <p>Coordinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rezos Brands | <p>Attendees</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christos Karras, Rezos Brands Anastasia Vlachou, Rezos Brands |
|--|--|

DIGITAL Advanced Digital Skills Meeting | 24th of October, 2023 1/29/2024 | 28

SPECIALISED Second Call

SPECTRO

Specialised Education programmes in Cybersecurity and Robotics

Description

Specialised Education programmes in Cybersecurity and Robotics (SPECTRO) focuses on the design and delivery of two double-degree master's programmes in two key digital technology areas for the future of Europe: 1) Cybersecurity and 2) Robotics. The two specialised master's programmes, which also include a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship, are designed and delivered by a consortium consisting of 12 higher education institutions from 7 different countries, 2 innovative SMEs, 1 leading research centre in Information Systems and EIT Digital, a pan-European organisation with in-depth knowledge and experience in the digital skills domain.

Start date: 01/09/2023
End date: 31/08/2027

Coordinator
▪ EIT Digital

Attendees
▪ Salvatore Moccia, EIT Digital
▪ Andrea Biancini, EIT Digital

OTHER INITIATIVES

DIGITAL SKILLS AND JOBS PLATFORM

The home of digital skills and jobs initiatives in Europe and the heart of the Digital Skills and Jobs Community.

The DSJP provides a wide range of high-quality information, resources and opportunities in the area of digital skills and jobs across all levels, from very basic to advanced. Up-to-date insights are offered in an accessible way to new users, while more experienced professionals can benefit from targeted content relevant to their field of expertise.

Additionally, a collaborative space is available for Community members to network, interact and grow together.

The Platform offers: Insights into EU and national initiatives and actions supporting digital skills and jobs, training opportunities and career development support; good practices, expert advice, resources and tools, data, research-based facts and figures, funding opportunities and financial instruments, thriving interactive community spaces, news, opinions and events.

digital-skills-jobs.europa.eu

Tomislava Recheva
Eleonora Censorii
European Schoolnet

EmpowerED

EmpowerED, running from 2023 to 2025, aims to establish a pan-European network and platform for exchanges between European EdTech initiatives, support organisations, practitioners, and policymakers. The project will map the EdTech landscape in Europe to reflect the current state of play in the sector. This will provide insight into trends linked to new schooling models and innovative education solutions.

www.empowerededtech.eu

Françoise Van Hemelryck
Romane Leaute
European Schoolnet

DS4Skills

Data Space for Skills aims to identify relevant data sources for the skills data space based on stakeholders' needs and propose conceptual approaches for the future deployment of the European Data Space for Skills. Via the wide and multidisciplinary network of partners, the project will build consensus and engage with the broad community of skills stakeholders.

www.skillsdataspace.eu

Marie Montaldo
DIGITALEUROPE

ANNEX 4 – CHALLENGE SCOPING OUTCOMES

Challenge	Note	Category
1 Rate of tech development and convergence – skills fit for industry	Resources available to SMEs- they trust universities; lack special funding.	Barriers to access
	No Cross - discipline Perspective	Fragmentation
	Funding and costs => Profit/cost (SMEs particularly)	ROI
	Lack of market demand for product/services needing advanced technology	ROI
	Companies have short-term vision; not investing in reskilling	ROI
	Short term vision	ROI
	Structures for changing content are cumbersome and increase cost of delivery. Mentoring can help keep content up to date	Speed of evolution
	Some policies. E.g.: GDPR related in need of better "governance" over new technologies or social issues (like data management + protection)	Speed of evolution
	Accreditations	Speed of evolution
	Lack of regulatory standardisation certification	Speed of evolution
	Technology companies will have to hire IT experts => afraid to approach new tech	Status Quo
	Lack of structure interest /opinions /attackers of advanced tech	Status Quo
	Keeping the Status Quo	Status Quo
	Lack of work force	Talent source
	Acceleration of digital transformation in the post-Covid time is facing a big hurdle: the NON-ICT converted workers and ability to uptake new technologies.	Talent source
2 Accessing the expertise for skilling – the bottleneck in developing the	Attract students to STEM (not only job opportunity but also impact)	Awareness
	Number of Students: Lack of promotion for digital skills as a relevant topic accross the whole education path	Awareness
	Lack of use and access to private sector tech labs in education	Barriers to access
	Very specialised knowledge / skills	Barriers to access

advanced digital talent pool	Train on ADS is costly. How to finance ADS training from public sector	Cost of delivery
	Lack of existing trainers in EU (sourcing from abroad can be expensive)	Cost of delivery
	Teaching staff: difficulties to compete with private salaries	Cost of delivery
	Not enough awareness on the ADS that could be integrated in existing courses across disciplines (Agri, health, etc.)	Fragmentation
	Institutions do not always have engagement with industry to discuss academic issues, including the creation and modification courses.	Fragmentation
	Attractiveness of Careers in teaching HE	Other
	The institutional procedure to create (even modify) a degree in an University / Institution is not agile in several aspects: - Internal design - Curriculum design - Institutional approval - Accreditation process - Student Enrolment	Status Quo
	Young students will become useless (demography) How politics will react to that?	Talent source
3 Addressing SMEs	Funding processes from government funds (HE) are too complex (bureaucracy). SMEs cannot afford the administrative work behind the funding (reporting, no cashflow, etc.). We have talked about European funds, rather than government/national.	Administrative burden
	Support for adult learners is lower than for other types	Barriers to access
	SMEs are ill-equipped with staff holding basic digital skills to take advantage of novel technologies. Only IT departments possess of the know-how.	Fragmentation
	Time poor organisations	Limited resources
	Workload is high and limited capacity to add in time	Limited resources
	Multirole nature of the SME employee compared to large corporates	Limited resources
	Lack of resources in SMEs to invest in ADS. Prioritisation of SMEs to invest in areas where the need is identified as bigger.	ROI
	Lack of perspective on how an investment in ADS can yield greater revenue	ROI
Lack of recognising or understanding the need of ADS in the industry and subsequently in SMEs.	ROI	

	Lack of leaders recognising the importance of integrating ADS in daily lives. False perception that the provision of this is a luxury.	ROI
	Lack of internal leadership in digital	ROI
	Visionary thinking missing.	ROI
	Understanding the real demand and urgency	ROI
3 Addressing SMEs (Group 2)	Procurement policies	Administrative burden
	Deficit of (economic) policy	Administrative burden
	Lack of support (for women) to upskills and proceed in career	Awareness
	Integration of Solutions	Barriers to access
	Lack of EU-wide frameworks	Fragmentation
	Lack of policy support to this purpose.	Fragmentation
	Deficit of (economic) policy	Other
	Legislative development that can impact business activities as a whole	Other
	Lack of visible reward / system for companies that understand the importance of training	ROI
	SMEs are reluctant to adapt to the fast technological evolution due to the rising costs that will come	ROI
	Evolution / Disruption thorough novel technologies, that make forms of work or even jobs altogether less important	Speed of evolution
	Working toward a common framework	Speed of evolution
Recognition of skills & currciulum	Speed of evolution	
4 Finding candidates at the right level - the supply of candidates for very advanced programmes	Admission to market studies is limited by bachelor degree.	Barriers to access
	Lack of test funds, open laboratories for everyone to try the technology	Barriers to access
	Lack of advanced digital tools in same sectors	Barriers to access
	Companies have needs 'now', they do not invest in a long-term vision of employers	Limited resources
	Why shall I complete an advanced degree that I could have had before?	Other
	Personal responsibility in the adoption of in practice advanced tech	Other

	Self confidence, working in STEM is difficult for women	Other
	Lack of regulation in specific sectors	Speed of evolution
	societal barriers to adoption of AI in practice	Status Quo
	Lack of role models in advanced technology sectors	Status Quo
	No role models around to follow the new path	Systemic
5 The need for domain expertise and sectoral divergence in demands (Group 2)	Access to technology	Barriers to access
	Funding is too fragmented	Fragmentation
	No transversal/ multidisciplinary approach in formal education: programs are still too sectorial	Fragmentation
	Speed of Tech development is fast, with the education sector struggling to keep up with integrating and addressing developments in their courses.	Speed of evolution
	Not everyone has the financial capability to attend courses	Barriers to access
	Investment pipeline: the more specific, the less stakeholders	Cost of delivery
	Lack of communication between stakeholders - gaps, mismatches, no synergies	Fragmentation
	division technical - strategic roles	Fragmentation
	Lack of simple communication of technology by sectors	Fragmentation
	Education system must be practical	Other
	Organisations give up the present > become agile	ROI
	Speed of tech development	Speed of evolution
	Lack of regulations at global level	Speed of evolution
Rigidity of education system: - teaching methods, length, difficulty to change programmes, speeds) - not thinking outside the box	Status Quo	
	Tech industry is white-male dominated	Barriers to access

6 The leaky pipeline of women in digital	The technology industry, particularly in software development and gaming, is predominantly white-male dominated, leading to a perceived need for greater encouragement of female participation due to a hostile environment with perceived low levels of female-centered games and developers.	Systemic
	Lack of quota for women in - BoD - Senior executive positions	Systemic
	Childcare availability	Systemic
	Lack of appropriate support or family support leaves for raising / having kids	Systemic
	Ingrained Sexism: Guided education at birth based on gender --> Lack of (supporting) female role models / mentoring	Systemic
	Lack of appropriate guidance	Systemic
	Hostile work environment	Systemic
	Gender-biased technology	Systemic

ANNEX 5 - IDENTIFIED ACTIONS

Challenge 1: Rate of Tech Development and Convergence – Skills Fit for Industry						
TYPE	SUBTYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT	EFFORT	COEFF.
Programme	Capacity Building	Content Validation Process	Validation of content by students, faculties, and external stakeholders.	5	3	1,67
Infrastructure	Tools	European Skills Gap Initiative	Establishment of a European-level effort to quickly define and address skills gaps.	5	5	1,00
Programme	Capacity Building	Skill-Specific Workshops	Hosting meetings/workshops dedicated to specific skills, regularly updated by educational institutions/private companies.	4	4	1,00
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	Flexible Accreditation Programmes	Allowance of more fluid programmes by accreditation agencies to adapt to changing needs.	3	3	1,00
Programme	Capacity Building	Integrated ADS University Courses	Regular updating and integration of all university courses with ADS, ensuring inclusion across majors/degrees.	3	5	0,60
Challenge 2: Accessing the Expertise for Skilling – The Bottleneck in Developing the Advanced Digital Talent Pool						
TYPE	SUBTYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT	EFFORT	COEFF.
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	EU Programme Alignment	Promotion of DIGITAL to align with common programmes like ERASMUS.	4	1	4,00
Infrastructure	Guidelines	Pre-BA/MSC Curricular Integration	Providing guidelines for restructuring curricula to include digital skills prior to BA/MSC level education.	4	2	2,00
Programme	Capacity Building	Advanced Skills Course Expansion	Building on existing courses with advanced skills tracks while developing new courses.	3	2	1,50
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	EU Accreditation Harmonisation	Linking/Harmonising accreditation processes within the EU for consistency.	3	4	0,75
Policy & Regulation	Incentivisation	AUGN Funding Allocation	Allocation of "Adult Upgrading Funding" with tech investments to address educational needs.	2,5	3	0,83

Challenge 3: Addressing SMEs						
TYPE	SUBTYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT	EFFORT	COEFF.
Policy & Regulation	Incentivisation	Public-Private Education Partnerships	Facilitation of public-private partnerships to enhance educational offerings.	4	1	4,00
Programme	Scholarships	Educational Funding Allocation	Allocation of greater funding and support to address educational needs of SMEs	4	1	4,00
Infrastructure	Networks and clusters	Networks and Clusters	Establishment of networks and clusters for collaborative learning and resource sharing.	3,5	1	3,50
Programme	Courses	Bite-Size Training Solutions	Provision of bite-size training and tech solutions to learners.	4	2	2,00
Programme	Courses	Executive ADS Education	Education for HR & CEOs, emphasising the importance of ADS for strategic decision-making.	5	3	1,67
Infrastructure	Tools	Education Opportunity Platform	Creation of a One-stop shop platform for educational opportunities.	4	3	1,33
Infrastructure	Tools	E-Wallet for Education	Development of an e-wallet (EID Wallet) for streamlined access to educational resources.	4	4	1,00
Programme	Courses	STEM and ADS Vocational Training	Implementation of vocational training targeting STEM and ADS fields.	4	4	1,00
Infrastructure	Guidelines	EU Digital Transformation Strategy	Development of a comprehensive digital transformation strategy at a European level.	3	3	1,00
Policy & Regulation	Incentivisation	ADS Training Incentives	Offering financial benefits for employees/SMEs to receive ADS training.	2,5	2,5	1,00
Challenge 4: Finding Candidates at the Right Level - The Supply of Candidates for Very Advanced Programmes						
TYPE	SUBTYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT	EFFORT	COEFF.
Infrastructure	Networks and clusters	Academic Engagement Initiative	Greater engagement with academic & sector societies to foster knowledge exchange.	3	1	3,00
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	Unified Competency Assessment	Application of unified competency portfolios for comprehensive assessment.	5	3	1,67
Communications and awareness	Communications and awareness	Role Model Programme Promotion	Promotion of educational programmes by role models to inspire participation.	5	3	1,67

Infrastructure	Tools	Candidate Engagement Pathways	Design of DSJP learning paths to attract and engage potential candidates.	4	3	1,33
Communications and awareness	Communications and awareness	Multidisciplinary Skill Encouragement	Encouragement of multidisciplinary application of skills across domains.	3	3	1,00

Challenge 5: The Need for Domain Expertise and Sectoral Divergence in Demands

TYPE	SUBTYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT	EFFORT	COEFF.
Policy & Regulation	Incentivisation	Private Resource Pooling	Pooling private resources for sectoral interests to enhance educational outcomes.	3	2	1,50
Infrastructure	Networks and clusters	Networks and Clusters	Establishment of networks and clusters for collaborative learning and resource sharing.	3	3	1,00
Communications and awareness	Communications and awareness	Digital Skills Public Awareness	Explanation of digital skills for the general public through media outreach.	3	3	1,00
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	Governance Agility Enhancement	Increasing governance agility at the political level for effective policy-making.	4	4	1,00
Programme	Scholarships	Erasmus Professional Mobility	Implementing Erasmus for professional mobility to facilitate cross-border learning opportunities.	5	5	1,00
Infrastructure	Tools	Sectoral Ecosystem Mapping	Mapping the sectoral ecosystem and digital trajectories for informed planning.	3	4	0,75
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	Flexible Education Strategies	Implementing flexible and creative education strategies to adapt to technological advancements.	3	5	0,60
Infrastructure	Networks and clusters	Multiprofessional EU Networks	Creating multidisciplinary and multiprofessional EU-digital networks for collaboration.	1	5	0,20
Policy & Regulation	Harmonisation	Microcredential Harmonisation	Harmonising EU-level mechanisms to certify microcredentials provided by VET activities.	1	5	0,20
Policy & Regulation	Incentivisation	Innovation-Focused Funding	Directing funding towards think tanks rather than projects to support innovation.	1	5	0,20

Challenge 6: The Leaky Pipeline of Women in Digital

TYPE	SUBTYPE	ACTION	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT	EFFORT	COEFF.
------	---------	--------	-------------	--------	--------	--------

Programme	Capacity Building	Teacher In-Service Training	Provision of in-service training for teachers to stay updated on career choices and new roles.	5	3	1,67
Programme	Courses	Tech Workshops for Girls	Conducting regular workshops for girls in the school curriculum to foster tech interest.	4	3	1,33
Policy & Regulation	Other	Childcare Policy Advocacy	Advocacy for policy change in childcare to support educational access.	5	4	1,25
Programme	Scholarships	Women in Software Initiatives	Creation of initiatives to encourage women in software development through scholarships.	2,5	2,5	1,00
Programme	Capacity Building	Career Guidance Training	Training for career guidance teachers to provide unbiased guidance for girls.	2,5	5	0,50

